

The AI LLM Antidote - Understanding the Difference Between Signals and Significance

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Abstract. In this paper, I argue that the future of human-AI collaboration - particularly in the context of large language model (LLM) adoption across organizations - will hinge on a fundamental cognitive and linguistic distinction: the difference between understanding *Signals* and understanding *Significance*. Drawing on the emerging economics of token-based AI consumption, organizational workforce trends, and the structural characteristics of English-language education in India, I contend that “Token Management” and “Prompt Engineering” will become defining professional competencies of the near future. I further state that AI LLMs, despite their apparent sophistication, are currently limited by output inconsistency - and that this inconsistency, rather than capability, is the primary barrier to large-scale job displacement. The antidote to AI-related career anxiety, I conclude, is not resistance but communicative precision: the ability to distinguish signal from significance.

1 Introduction

According to Sam Altman:

“AI will soon work like electricity or water; you’ll pay metered bills based on usage instead of fixed subscriptions.”

When you think of his statement about charging for AI LLMs, it is not just a possibility - it is a plausible outcome, given that every measure is eventually reduced (compressed/packed) to a property called “Token”.

2 What Is a Token?

Technically, a token is a unit of a chunk of text that an AI LLM processes. In simple terms, a token is a non-descriptive way of saying the work that is expected from, or done by, an AI LLM. Imagine electricity - you are charged a certain amount per unit. A unit is the measure of energy consumed over time (a kilowatt-hour, or kWh), simply displayed as “units” for the sake of simplicity, so people (laymen like us) can be charged based on units without needing to understand the work done and other difficult terminology in this context. In water, consumers are again charged in units. Think of units as packs - a pack could contain meters, liters, kilograms, tokens, etc. You get the idea.

Figure 1: Tokens as the AI equivalent of metered utility units (electricity, water).

3 Why Focus on Tokens and How Consumers Will Be Asked to Pay in the Future?

(Even though subscriptions can stay, based on a provider’s discretion.)

The simple answer is spending efficiency. Unlike time, which is unlimited given our understanding of the existence of known and unknown infinities, anything that can be measured definitively can be accounted for - but time itself cannot be monetized because it is indefinite. Only what time signifies, when the significance was realized, and how the significance was set in motion to begin with, helps with monetization. Look around you

and ask yourself if there was ever even a single instance of an invoice, a bill, or a receipt that charged you for *time* - time as a commodity, and not as a measure. Nowhere. This nature of time gives rise to what can be recorded as a reference to time, and that reference can be used as a commodity. That's where tokens come in: a digital commodity.

Figure 2: Conceptual comparison of flat subscription and metered (token-based) pricing. Under a simplified linear model, fixed subscription revenue can become unprofitable as usage grows, whereas metered pricing scales revenue with usage and helps preserve margins.

4 Significance as a Core Concept in Token Management

“Token Management” will be the next department all companies set up. There will be Token Managers, Token Analysts, Token Distributors - and more roles can be developed depending on a company’s direction and trajectory. This introduction of Token Management will be applicable to all companies using AI LLMs, one way or another. This, in turn, reintroduces “Prompt Engineering”, which for a brief moment popped up on our radar as the next promising career - and suddenly disappeared, as if it were an insignificant passing shot. Prompt Engineering will return as one of the most sought-after careers in the future. It would be so significant within a company that prompt engineers will be the first in line for promotions, appraisals, and appreciations - and will always be “in consideration” when it comes to demotions and job losses. Politics plays an important role here. Just so you know.

In the future, utilization of tokens will be the #1 KPI in any company using AI LLMs.

This will be accomplished through “Token Management” and “Prompt Engineering”, and will play a crucial role in the future of any company using AI LLMs.

#1 KPI: Token Utilisation

Figure 3: Primitive Representation of an organisational structure of a future Token Management department.

5 Signals and Significance: The Two Words That Will Make or Break Careers

Here’s the thing - people who don’t understand the difference between “Signals” and “Significance” will never hold a career in “Token Management” or “Prompt Engineering.” This translates to stunted growth. No second thoughts here. Companies will spend fortunes to educate their loosely educated employees to truly understand the importance of the work expected from them, based on “Signals” and “Significance.”

There will be other positions to fill if not for the highlights mentioned above, but their shelf-life will be limited, with diminishing returns because they will be considered positions expected to become a burden. This is not applicable to all positions, so don’t get me wrong, this potential burden driven mindset is only applicable to positions that can be replaced by AI LLM in the future.

In short, a company hires people who understand “Significance” with retention in mind and those who understand “Signals” with attrition in mind.

Figure 4: The Signal-Significance spectrum: from simply reacting to a sound, to fully understanding the true purpose.

6 Careers in the Future Will Not Be Built on Traditional Employment.

Careers as we know from a traditional standpoint will collapse or will be put on "deprecation" notice. New opportunities arise though, they are "Consultancy" and "Agency". Contracts, temporary work agreements and clause-based work will become the norm.

Recently, a company in India announced plans to equalize the headcount of employees in the company to the usage of AI LLM agents. In short, there would be one AI LLM agent for every employee - 1:1. Their plan is to halve the employee count and replace the other half with AI LLMs. This is not only a possibility but an expectation that will be met and exceeded in the future.

But the above implementation takes time - lots and lots of time (not an exaggeration) - because Indians, even though one of the largest English-speaking populations in the world, are not equipped to handle "Token Management" or "Prompt Engineering". This is because the majority of Indians understand "Signals" and not "Significance," and it starts with the English language.

Figure 5: Illustrative projection of the shift from human to AI LLM workforce share. Actual figures depend on adoption pace, regulation, and the development of Significance-based competencies.

7 The Role of the English Language in Prompt Engineering

Every prompt is more easily engineered in the English language, due to the lack of accents in the script.

How many people speak about prompting in other languages, and how many tutorials have you found that teach prompting in other languages? If there are any, they would not come close to what the English language can accomplish in prompting - by reducing unnecessary inclusions like accents in a prompt. The unnecessary is not about the script; it's about token usage. The most viable option for using the fewest tokens to get work done by an AI LLM, in comparison to other languages, is the English language. This reduces chunk size and, in actuality, increases propagation. Look around you - tell me where you don't find the English language. Nowhere.

In Indian companies, employees will be required to handle "Token Management" or "Prompt Engineering" to realize the 1:1 human-to-AI LLM agent ratio, or even to replace a quarter of the workforce. This is highly unlikely to happen in the near future. So what gives?

Well, in short - education.

The Indian education system has always promoted learning the English language through “Signals”, without understanding the “Significance.” All subjects (STEM, etc.) - except for the local languages - are in the English language. If any subject matter originally printed or propagated in the English language is taught in a local language, a carbon-copy translation is taught, rendering multilingual mediums of teaching technically useless. Even STEM education in India is based on “Signals” and not “Significance,” because when you only understand “Signals” (because of how you learn the English language), memorization is your only option - you cannot explore. The Indian education system promotes memorization, not thinking and reasoning. The fact that memorization is so vastly practiced is the reason why Indians cannot integrate easily into a purely English-speaking system. This is the reason why PhDs awarded by Indian universities are not taken seriously by most Western universities - though there may be exceptions.

This is also the reason why Indians who travel to English-speaking countries find it extremely difficult to assimilate, and instead choose to accumulate and find companionship among other Indians living abroad in similar situations. In short, the majority of the Indian population in the West are more comfortable speaking their local Indian languages than English. The West is confused about the Indian mind: “How can you have such a high degree of education and not speak the English language? In what language did you study? If it’s English, why do you have such a hard time communicating in English?” The answer to all these Westerners is this: the Indian minds living around you, whom you considered to be of very high caliber, are operating on “Signals” and not “Significance” - at least, the majority of them.

There is also a growing trend in the West of distancing from Indians, because it is impossible to have a conversation that flows with an Indian living abroad. Speak to an Indian in an English-speaking country and try to have a continuous conversation in English without tiring the Indian out. They smile, laugh, and show obedience only to escape the actuality of a mindset that was basically set up and developed in India by an education system that believed “Signals” is the route to education. The teachers don’t understand the English language themselves, yet continue to profess - because it’s their job, not because it’s important. This is where the “Significance” is lost.

Figure 6: The pathway from Signal-based Indian education to AI-readiness, and the Significance gap that currently blocks it.

8 An Illustrative Analogy: The Dog and Doglish

When you speak to your dog, it doesn't know whether you are speaking English, or whether it's a word, a phrase, or a sentence. It can identify the sound and respond accordingly - that's all. When you command your dog to sit, heel, or jump, it doesn't wonder why the human companion is expecting it to sit, heel, or jump in a commanding tone rather than a polite one. The dog simply obeys because a dog only understands the action, the posture, and the position associated with the sound it hears - rather than trying to decipher the usage of a particular word by the owner based on context.

Makes sense? When you tell your dog that you would speak “Doglish” at home and switch to English in public, your dog would not understand the “Significance” of the entire sentence. It doesn't know Doglish, home, switch, English, public, or every other conjunction, interjection, or adjective you decide to use as filler. This is “Signal”-based learning. Your dog instead tilts its head, thinking: *this human companion uttered a sound and I have absolutely no idea what to do with it.*

If you think this paper tries to undermine Indians - you couldn't be more wrong. In fact, this paper was written by an Indian living in India without a single stamp on his passport. So hold your horses.

9 Signals and Significance as a Safety Net in the AI LLM Ecosystem

Well, did you notice? Nowhere in this paper was there even a brief mention of the definition of “Signals” and “Significance.” Did you read anywhere that the paper said, “Hey, first let's define or understand the definition of ‘Signals’ and ‘Significance’ because they are the highlight”? No.

People who understand this paper understand “Significance.” People who don’t understand this paper understand “Signals.” There’s your difference.

“Signals” are proximal. “Significance” is affinitive.

Figure 7: How the shift from Proximal (Signal) interaction to Affinitive (Significance) comprehension acts as an ultimate career safety net against AI automation.

10 A Note on AI LLM Consistency

By the way, this paper is completely human-written. The paper was fed into AI LLMs multiple times to get the desired tone - and the AI LLM failed every time. The language produced was well-written, but it lost the essence. And worst of all, the same AI LLM churned out different results when the same text was input, signalling major inconsistency. Even though AI LLM corrected the basic punctuation, grammatical errors in this writing, the paper had to be rewritten to match the exact tone, wording and structure of the raw paper in its entirety. Therefore, until AI LLMs become consistent in their output, the traditional job takeover is nowhere close to the near future - because until consistency is maintained, no output can be considered usable in its strictest sense.

So all the people out there worried about an AI LLM takeover of jobs need not worry, because consistency is the provider’s prerogative and burden, which translates to token usage. This conflict is not likely to get fixed in the near future, and will most likely be the cause of future lawsuits against AI LLM providers. Also, companies deciding to replace human potential with AI LLMs now will hire back people who understand “Significance,” without batting an eyelid, in the future.

Figure 8: Illustration of AI LLM output variance when the same prompt is submitted multiple times. Inconsistency remains the primary obstacle to reliable job automation.

11 The AI LLM Antidote

The fact that AI LLM is made out to be that giant monster here to destroy everybody's future is very entertaining to hear or watch - it's like a well-funded and well-produced Hollywood movie. But AI LLMs are nowhere near causing the catastrophe most dystopians force upon us. AI LLMs will only disrupt convenience at its peak. The only antidote is to understand "Signals" and "Significance."

Let's look at a simple example. How you explain things to an AI LLM becomes paramount when you feed questions into it - and also how the results evaluate to true.

11.1 Scenario 1

HUMAN: "What is 3+3?"

AI LLM: "The answer is 6."

The above question seems harmless, and the answer is perfect - right? Wrong. Let's consider every character as a token, so every letter and space equals 1 token. There are 27 tokens spent in this fairly simple-looking question and answer.

11.2 Scenario 2

HUMAN: “3+3?”

AI LLM: “6”

The token count in this scenario is 4.

Figure 9: Token cost comparison: verbose natural-language prompt (Scenario 1) vs. precision prompt (Scenario 2). Both yield identical output; Scenario 2 consumes 85% fewer tokens.

Scenario 1 and Scenario 2 output the same answer. The former was formatted as a sentence; the latter was a straightforward result. A person who understands “Signals” wouldn’t find a difference. A person who understands “Significance” will. Who do you think saved tokens and money for the company?

If you can understand this, you will deal with less headache and anxiety in the future - and stop blaming AI LLMs for taking away your job. Your job now is not to find employment or to keep your existing employment by hook or crook, but to realize the disruption of convenience and get better at communication. A good communicator will always understand “Significance.”

“Signals” and “Significance” - that’s your AI LLM antidote.

12 Conclusion

The coming era of token-based AI LLM consumption will separate professionals not by technical skill, but by communicative depth. Token Management and Prompt Engineering will rise as foundational organizational competencies. The English language, by virtue of its token efficiency, will remain the dominant medium of human-AI interaction. Education systems - particularly in India - must evolve from Signal-based memorization to Significance-based reasoning to prepare their populations for this shift. And above all, the inconsistency of current AI LLM outputs remains the most honest safeguard against catastrophic job displacement - at least for now.

Figure 10: Summary comparison between the outgoing traditional era and the incoming AI Token era, underscoring the shift toward Significance-based reasoning and communicative precision.

Author Note

I wrote this paper entirely without AI assistance in composition. I fed the paper into AI LLMs multiple times in an attempt to replicate its tone - and it failed each time. This outcome is itself cited within the paper as evidence for the AI LLM consistency argument. I invite readers to contribute corrections collaboratively - a practice I call “Collective Corrections.”

I wrote this paper after taking the assessment in the [Psynormic Velocity Profile](#). Psynormic helps you understand “Signals” and “Significance” for free.

Competing Interests

I declare no competing interests, except for an affiliation with the Psynormic Velocity Profile, a tool I created referenced in the Author Note.

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